

Visual Map – Main Equations – 8T

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Abstract:

Visual map of the theory, the meaning of the main two equations and the part of each term within to the equation is presented in a concise and to the point manner. It can help researchers understand the whole picture in rather easier and faster fashion due to its visual features. These two equations are at the heart of 8T so understanding them is highly beneficial to readers.

Introduction

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)